

FRUITS AND VEGETABLES CONSUMPTION AMONG STUDENTS IN OSUN STATE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, ILESA, OSUN STATE

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Abstract

Dietary patterns rich in high fruits and vegetables intake are associated with a myriad of health benefits. Dietary habits of young adult is in limelight, as this group is in transition from adolescence to adulthood and are potential to influence the health status of next generation. This study determined the fruits and vegetables consumption among students in Osun State College of Education Ilesa. Descriptive survey research design was used in the study. Five research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study consisted of ten thousand, seven hundred and five (10,705) students. Proportional and simple random sampling technique was used to select two percent (2%) of the population. Data was collected using a structured, food frequency and four-point-scale questionnaire. Two hundred and fourteen (214) copies of questionnaire were administered to students in all the five schools in the College. Frequency count, simple percentage, mean and t-test were used to analyze the data collected. Findings showed that the students in Osun State College of Education were aware of the importance of fruits and vegetables consumption and were also exposed to variety of fruits and vegetables. However, the consumption pattern of fruits and vegetables among the College students was generally low, 4.67% of respondents consumed fruits and vegetables at the recommended amount (five times per day). The main factors that influence consumption were price in the market, freshness, health benefits, fruits and vegetables in season, taste/appearance, availability of money to spend, and availability of variety of fruits and vegetables on campus. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that the students in Osun state College of Education be more enlightened on the benefits of fruits and vegetables consumption pattern.

Keywords: Fruits, vegetables, students, dietary pattern, health.

Introduction

Fruits and vegetables consumption is crucial to the availability of micronutrients to the body. This is because these food items are a rich source of vitamins and minerals which are required for normal functioning of the human body. Although required in small proportions, vitamins and minerals are needed in the diet as the human body is not able to synthesize them in sufficient amount to meet the Recommended Dietary Allowances (RDA) or Recommended Daily Intake of vitamins and minerals (Adedeji & Ogboru, 2013)

Apart from providing micronutrients, fruits and vegetables are known to provide dietary fibres (soluble and insoluble) which are vital for the optimal functioning of the gastro-intestinal tract. Besides their aesthetic value in food presentation, fruits and vegetables also enable the body to use other nutrients required for its normal functioning, like energy from fats and carbohydrates (Adedeji & Ogboru, 2013; Esterhuyse, Oguntibeju & Truter, 2013).

Regular consumption of fruits and vegetables is associated with a myriad of health benefits. Maintenance of health of young adults in a country is of paramount importance. Young adults aged between 18 and 24 years are in a stage of life to make their own food choice. Moreover, this is the age at which many students secure admission into universities and colleges and commence tertiary education. In nutritional studies, the eating behaviors and food choice of College students are determined by interaction of various factors. These are biological (changing energy demand and weight change) and socio cultural (availability of food, prices and culture) (Madhujith & Perera, 2012).

There is mounting evidence to the effect that bioactives present in fruits and vegetables help to prevent against a number of diseases such as coronary heart diseases, hypertension and cancers (British Dietetic Association, 2011). Thus, the general advice is to consume significant proportion of fruits and vegetables to ensure the protection from Non Communicable Diseases (NCDs). In this context, World Health Organization (WHO) has set standards with respect to consumption of fruits and vegetables by recommending a minimum of 400g per day, per capital (WHO, 2004). Values below the above requirement is said to be responsible for the increase incidence of cardiovascular diseases

as well as cancer, which are among the major leading causes of death worldwide (Adedeji & Ogboru, 2013).

Currently, Non Communicable Diseases (NCDS) had overtaken Communicable Diseases (CD) and are now the leading causes of mortality, morbidity and disability (WHO, 2011). The World Health Organization (WHO) (2004), estimated that low fruits and vegetables consumption contribute to approximately 2.7 million death per year from chronic disease, 11% of Cardiovascular Accidents (CVA), 31% of Ischemic Heart Disease (IHD), 14% of gastrointestinal cancer and 9% of strokes death worldwide. In 2011, World Health Organization (WHO) reported that, low fruits and vegetables intake is among the top sixth selected risk factors for global mortality, morbidity and disability (WHO, 2011). Apart from their food value, they also serve as medicine; they have abilities to cure most diseases in man, particularly the central nervous system ailments (FAO, 2003).

It has been observed that majority of College students do not know the benefits of consuming fruits and vegetables as part of their daily food intake. Some of the world most widespread and debilitating nutritional disorders, including birth defects, mental and physical retardation, weakened immune systems, blindness and even death, are caused by diets lacking in vitamins and minerals (commonly referred to as micronutrients). Low fruit and vegetable consumption is a major contributory factor to such micro-nutrient deficiencies (FAO, 2003).

This research work therefore focused into fruits and vegetables consumption among students in Osun State College of Education, Ilesa in order to proffer possible solutions on how to improve their fruits and vegetables consumption and prevents them from chronic diseases.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the fruits and vegetables consumption among students in Osun State College of Education, Ilesa. Specifically the study:

1. identified the knowledge of students on fruits and vegetables consumption
2. determined the variety of fruits and vegetables that are available to the College students.

3. identified the fruits and vegetables consumption pattern of the College students
4. determined the different factors influencing fruits and vegetables consumption among the College students.
5. suggested ways of improving the consumption of fruits and vegetables among the College students.

Research Questions

The following questions were generated to guide the study:

1. What is the knowledge of the College students on fruits and vegetables consumption?
2. What are the varieties of fruits and vegetables the College students are exposed to?
3. What is the pattern of fruits and vegetables consumption among the College students?
4. What are the different factors influencing fruits and vegetables consumption among College students?
5. What are the ways of improving the consumption of fruits and vegetables among College students?

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the pattern of fruits and vegetables consumption between male and female students.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the opinions of male and female students on the factors influencing fruits and vegetables consumption among College students.

Methodology

The design used for this study was the descriptive survey research design. Descriptive survey design solicits information on the opinions, beliefs and ideas of respondents without interfering with their opinions.

The study was carried out in Osun State College of Education, Ilesa, Osun State. Osun State College of Education is one of the tertiary institutions in Ilesa town. It is located in Ilesa East Local Government Area of Osun State. Ilesa East Local Government Area is one of the thirty one (31) Local Governments in Osun State. Osun State College of Education (formally Oyo State College of Education) Ilesa was established in 1978 during the

Administration of Brigadier (now Rtd. Major General) David M. Jemibewon as the military governor of Oyo State. The college is organized in accordance with provisions of the National Commission for College of Education (NCCE) into five major academic units/division styled schools, each of which is made up of a number of Departments. The schools are: School of Education, Arts and Social Sciences, Languages, Vocational and Technical Education and School of Science.

The population for the study was all the students in Osun state College of Education Ilesa. The total population of students is ten thousand seven hundred and five (10,705). There are five thousand eight hundred and ninety two (5,892) female and four thousands eight hundred and thirteen (4,813) male students in all the five schools (Division of Academic Affairs, 2013).

Two percent (2%) of the population was used for the study, using proportional and simple random sampling technique to select two hundred and fourteen (214) out of ten thousand seven hundred and five (10,705) students.

<i>Name of schools</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>
Arts and social sciences	2,708	54
Education	1,162	23
Languages	1008	21
Sciences	4649	92
Vocational and technical	1178	24
Total	10,705	214

Source: Division of Academic Affairs, 2013

A structured, food frequency and four-point-scale questionnaire was used to solicit, information from respondents. The research questionnaire consisted of two sections; Section A and B. Section A consisted of personal data of the respondents and Section B, fixed response items based on research questions.

The instrument for data collection was subjected to face and content validation by three experts in Food and Nutrition. They were requested to check whether the items were relevant to the study and that the instrument would solicit the information required from the frame work of the research questions.

Two hundred and twenty (220) copies of questionnaire were produced and administered personally to the respondents and the

filled copies of questionnaire were collected immediately to avoid loss of questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed by the researcher to students from the five schools in Osun State College of Education Ilesa. The administration of the questionnaire was supervised by the researcher; the responses were collected and analyzed.

Mean (\bar{X}) and T-test statistical tools were used to analyse the data collected for the study. The mean of the questionnaire items was used and was interpreted based on the statistical real limits of the numbers as follows;

Response Category Boundary	Point	Limit
Strongly agree (SA)	4	3.50 - 4.00
Agree (A)	3	2.50 - 3.49
Disagree (D)	2	1.50 - 2.49
Strongly disagree(SD)	1	0.50 - 1.49

A mean of 2.50 was accepted as agreed

T-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance was used to test the null hypotheses for the study. The decision rule applied was that when $t\text{-cal} < t\text{-tab}$, the null hypothesis is accept, when $t\text{-cal} > t\text{-tab}$, the null hypothesis is reject.

Results

Table 1: Personal Data of Respondents

S/N	Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Age:		
	15-20	86	40.19
	21-30	120	56.07
	31-40	5	2.34
	41-50	3	1.40
	50 above	0	0
	Total	214	100
2.	Sex:		
	Male	107	50
	Female	107	50
	Total	214	100

3.	Religion:		
	Christianity	149	69.63
	Islam	64	29.91
	Traditional	1	0.47
	Total	214	100
4.	Ethnic Group		
	Yoruba	202	94.39
	Igbo	11	5.14
	Hausa	0	0
	Other	1	0.47
	Total	214	100
5.	Name of School		
	Arts and social science	54	25.23
	Education	23	10.75
	Languages	21	9.81
	Science	92	43.00
	Vocational and Technical	24	11.21
	Total	214	100
6.	Academic Year		
	One	65	30.40
	Two	46	21.49
	Three	82	38.32
	Four	21	9.81
	Total	214	100
7.	Educational level		
	NCE Students	134	62.62
	Degree students	80	37.40
	Total	214	100

The distribution above shows that a little over half (56.07%) of the respondents were between 21 and 30 years of age, followed by 40.19% who were in the 15 to 20 years of age. 50% of the respondents were males and 50% were females. Two thirds (69.63%) were Christians, 29.91% were Muslims and 0.47% were traditional worshippers. Almost all the respondents (94.40%) were Yorubas and 5.14% were Igbos. The highest percentage of respondents (43%) were from Science and 9.81% were from Languages. There were more NCE students (62.62%) than Degree students (37.40%).

Research Question 1: What is the knowledge of the College students on fruits and vegetables consumption?

Table 2: Responses on knowledge of the College students on fruits and vegetables consumption

S/N	ITEMS	YES		NO	
		F	%	F	%
1.	Knowledge of the (WHO) recommended amount to be consumed	199	92.99	15	7.01
2.	Fruits and vegetables are good sources of photo chemicals	204	95.33	10	4.67
3.	Fruits and vegetables contain Vitamins A, B & C	209	97.66	5	2.34
4.	Cooking methods reduce the nutritional values in fruits and vegetables	180	84.11	34	15.89
5.	Fruits and vegetables contain iron and potassium	200	93.46	14	6.54
6.	Fresh fruits are more nutritious than processed fruits	188	87.85	26	12.15

Table 2 above shows that 93.00% of respondents had the knowledge of the (WHO) recommended amount to be consumed, 95.33% knew that fruits and vegetables are good sources of phyto chemicals, 97.7% of respondents knew that fruits and vegetables contain vitamins A, B & C. 84.11% had the knowledge that cooking methods reduced the nutritional values in fruits and vegetables while 93.46% were aware that fruits and vegetables contain iron and potassium. 87.85% of respondents were aware that fresh fruits are more nutritious than processed fruits.

Research Question 2: What are the varieties of fruits and vegetables the College students are exposed to?

Table 3: Response on variety of fruits and vegetables the college students are exposed to.

S/N	ITEMS	Yes		No	
		F	%	F	%
1.	Fresh tropical/exotic fruits like, pineapples, pawpaw, mango, banana	202	94.39	12	5.61
2.	Apples, pear, local pear (ube), guava	192	89.72	22	10.28
3.	Fresh citrus fruits like oranges, grapes, limes, lemons, tangerines	187	87.38	27	12.62
4.	Berries like strawberries, kiwi fruits, blue berries	175	81.78	39	18.22
5.	Tomatoes, water melon, sugar cane	200	93.46	14	6.54
6.	Processed fruits like five alive, chivita, fumman etc	177	82.71	37	17.29
7	Non-leafy vegetables like okro, garden egg, carrot	191	89.25	23	10.75
8	Green leafy vegetables like spinach, pumpkin (Ugwu), water leaf, soko "Ewedu"	194	90.65	20	9.35
9	Special vegetables like lettuce, cabbage, cucumber	195	91.12	19	8.8

Table 3 above shows that 94.39% of the respondents consumed fresh tropical/exotic fruits, 89.72% consumed apples, pear and guava. 87.38% consumed fresh citrus fruits, 81.78% consumed berries, 93.46% consumed tomatoes, watermelon and sugar cane, 82.71% consumed processed fruits, while 89.25% consumed non- leafy vegetables, 90.65% consumed green leafy vegetables while 91.12% consumed special vegetables like cucumber and cabbage

Research Question 3: What is the pattern of fruits and vegetables consumption among the college students?

Table 4: Responses on consumption pattern of fruits and vegetables among college students

S / N	Item	Once per day		Twice per day		Three times per day		Five times per day		1-3 times per week		4-6 times week		Never	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Fresh citrus fruits like Orange, Lemon etc	134	62.62	39	18.22	19	8.88	2	0.93	14	6.54	4	1.87	2	0.93
2	Tropical exotic fruit like Pawpaw	118	55.14	54	25.23	15	7.01	2	0.93	22	10.28	0	0	3	1.40
3	Fruit juice like fuman five alive	120	56.07	40	18.69	9	4.21	4	1.87	26	12.15	5	2.34	10	4.67
4	Green leafy vegetables like Spinach, Pumpkin	101	47.20	51	23.83	20	9.35	1	0.47	25	11.68	1	0.47	6	2.80
5	Special vegetables like Lettuce, Cucumber, Cabbage	99	46.26	44	20.56	11	5.14	3	1.40	36	16.82	9	4.21	12	5.61
6	Non-leafy vegetables like Okro, Garden egg.	115	53.74	36	16.82	15	7.01	9	4.21	29	13.55	5	2.34	5	2.34
7	Tomatoes, Water melon, Apples	97	45.33	50	23.36	26	12.15	4	1.87	30	14.02	4	1.87	3	1.40
8	Berries like Straw berries, Kiwifruit, Blue berries	106	49.53	45	21.03	13	6.07	6	2.80	15	7.01	3	1.40	26	12.15

Table 4 above shows that 62.62% of respondents consumed fresh citrus fruits (like orange, lemon) once per day. 25.23% consumed tropical exotic fruits like pawpaw twice per day. Only 12.15% consumed tomatoes, watermelon and apples three times per day, while 4.67% consumed green leafy vegetables (like spinach, pumpkin) five times per day. 16.82% consumed special vegetables (like lettuce, cucumber, cabbage) 1-3 times per week

while 4.67% never consumed berries (like Straw berries, Kiwifruit and Blue berries).

Research Question 4: What are the different factors influencing fruits and vegetables consumption pattern among College students?

Table 5: Mean rating of responses on different factors influencing fruits and vegetables consumption pattern among College students.

S/N	Items	Frequency				Mean \bar{x}	Remarks
		SA	A	SD	D		
1	Freshness of the fruits and vegetables	114	84	13	3	3.44	Agreed
2	Prices in the market	90	92	22	10	3.22	Agreed
3	Availability of money to spend	84	105	20	5	3.25	Agreed
4	Taste/appearance	96	89	18	11	3.26	Agreed
5	Likeness/preference for some fruits and vegetables	92	102	14	6	2.84	Agreed
6	Fruits and vegetables in season	94	92	20	8	3.27	Agreed
7	Health benefits	102	83	18	11	3.25	Agreed
8	Lack of availability and variety of fruits produce on campus	83	88	19	24	3.07	Agreed
9	Lack of important places to buy the existing fresh fruits and vegetables	85	84	23	22	3.08	Agreed

SA= Strongly Agreed, A= Agreed, SD= Strongly Disagreed, D= Disagreed, \bar{x} = mean responses of respondents, R= Remark

Table 5, above shows that respondents agreed to all the factors listed above, as their means are above the cut-off point of 2.50.

Research Question 5: What are the ways of improving the consumption pattern of fruits and vegetables among college students?

Table 6: Mean rating of responses on the ways of improving the consumption pattern of fruits and vegetables among College students

S/N	Items	Frequency				Mean \bar{X}	Remark
		SA	A	SD	D		
1	Storage facilities should be improved upon	133	76	3	2	3.58	Agreed
2	Nutrition education should be organized for students on the health benefits of consumption of fruits and vegetables	124	83	6	1	3.54	Agreed
3	Availability of fruits and vegetables on and around the campus	82	98	20	14	3.15	Agreed
4	Advertisement of fruits and vegetables in different ways on campus (television, radio, poster, banner	86	87	22	19	3.12	Agreed
5	Having farmers market on campus	102	82	17	13	3.27	Agreed
6	Considerable amount from income should be budgeted on fruits and vegetables	86	88	20	20	3.12	Agreed

Table 6, shows that respondents agreed to all the six items listed above, as their means are above the cutoff point of 2.50.

Hypothesis 1 (Ho₁)

There is no significant difference in the pattern of fruits and vegetables consumption between male and female students.

Table 7: T- test analysis of male and female students on the pattern of fruits and vegetables consumption

Variable	N	\bar{X}	Df	t-cal	t-tab	Remark
Female (X)	8	29.50	14	1.10	2.14	Not significant
Male (Y)	8	27.39				

The calculated t-value (t-cal) of 1.10 is less than the table value (t-tab) of 2.14 at 14 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance i.e. $t\text{-cal} < t\text{-tab}$. Hence the null hypothesis of no difference is therefore accepted. This indicates that, there was no significant difference in the pattern of fruits and vegetables consumption between male and female students. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is upheld.

Hypothesis 2 (H_{o2})

There is no significant difference in the opinions of male and female students on the factors influencing fruit and vegetables consumption among college students.

Table 8: T-test analysis of male and female students on the factors influencing fruits and vegetables consumption

Variable	N	\bar{X}	df	t-cal	t-tab	Remark
Female (X)	9	88.69	16	2.14	2.12	Significant
Male(Y)	9	84.94				

According to decision rule, the calculated t- value (t- cal) of 2.14 is greater than the critical or table value (t- tab) of 2.12 at 16 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Thus the null hypothesis is hereby rejected and alternative hypothesis upheld. This shows that there was significant difference in the opinions of male and females students on the factors influencing fruits and vegetables consumption.

Discussions

The findings of this study established that the college students have knowledge of fruits and vegetables consumption. This agrees with Madhujith and Parera (2012) who revealed that students demonstrated a high level of knowledge of the health benefits of eating fruits and vegetables. The US Department of Health and Human services and US Department of Agriculture (2010),

however stated that students were unaware of health benefits of fruits and vegetables consumption.

This study also discovered that the College Students were exposed to variety of fruits and vegetables, the most frequently consumed fruits were fresh tropical/exotic fruits like, pineapple, pawpaw, mango, banana and others, and the vegetables were green leafy vegetables like spinach, pumpkin and others. Adedeji and Ogboru, (2013) stated that the most commonly consumed fruits were fresh tropical/exotic fruits like banana, pawpaw and others, the vegetables were green leafy vegetables like "Ewedu" (*chorcorus olitorus*), pumpkin and others. Consumer Finances and Socio – Economic Survey (2004) also supporting these findings stated that mango and banana are found to be the highest consumed fruits and the most consumed vegetables were leafy vegetables.

The inadequate pattern of consumption of fruits and vegetables recorded in this study was much lower than the recommended amount by World Health Organisation (WHO), (2011). The findings of this study was also lower than those of Liming,(2004) who stated that 32.5% of college students consumed fruits twice per day, and 26.3% consumed vegetables three times per day. Madhujith and Perera (2012) opined that 32% of American Students consumed the minimum numbers of five serving of fruits and vegetables each day. WHO (2004) stated in their study of twenty one developed countries (to determine national average fruits and vegetables consumption) that only three (Israel, Spain and Italy) had acceptable national average intake of at least 400kg/day or 5 or more servings.

The findings of this study was much better than that of US Department of Health and Human services and US Department of Agriculture (2010), which stated that 28.5% of students ate fruits once per day and 33.2% of students ate vegetables once per day. Consumption pattern among college students was low. National Health and Medical Research council recommended that adults should eat at least five kinds of vegetables and two kinds of fruits every day (NHMRC, 2005). Consumption pattern of fruits and vegetables among college students revealed that majority of the respondents consumed fruits and vegetables once per day and three times per week respectively. Only few of the students

consumed fruits and vegetables twice and five times per day respectively. Therefore, majority of the students did not meet daily recommendation of fruits and vegetables by World Health Organization (WHO, 2011).

Factors which influenced consumption of fruits and vegetables included freshness of the fruits and vegetables, prices in the market, availability of money to spend, taste/ appearance, likeness/preference for some fruits and vegetables, fruits and vegetables in season, health benefits, lack of availability and variety of fruits and vegetables produced on campus and lack of importance places to buy the existing fresh fruits and vegetables. This is in line with the research findings of Liming (2004), who stated that income level, preference, availability of food, and market prices influence fruits and vegetables consumption. Daniel and Ugwu (2009) also claimed that income, availability, knowledge and gender show significant effect on fruits and vegetables consumption

Furthermore, the findings on the ways of improving the consumption pattern of fruits and vegetables among College students revealed that, respondents agreed with all items identified in Table 6. The respondents supported the idea of organizing nutritional education for students on the health benefits of consumption of fruits and vegetables. This is in accordance with the research findings of Madhujith & Perera, (2012), who stated that nutritional education, mass media (Radio, Television and Online programme) as well as Technology promote the consumption of fruits and vegetables. Technology has helped in extending the harvest period and improvement of storage facilities, which are important for fruits and vegetables preservation. This was also supported by Liu (2003), who stated that nutritional education, policy and environmental approaches can increase the consumption of fruits and vegetables.

With regards to the hypotheses tested, hypothesis one revealed that there was no significant difference in the pattern of fruits and vegetables consumption between male and female students. Therefore the hypothesis of no significant difference was upheld. While hypothesis two revealed that there was significant difference in the opinions of male and female students on the factors influencing fruits and vegetables consumption among

College students. Therefore the null hypothesis was rejected and alternative hypothesis upheld.

Conclusion

The students in Osun State College of Education have knowledge of fruits and vegetables consumption. The College students were exposed to a variety of fruits and vegetables. The consumption pattern of fruits and vegetables among the College students was generally low, (majority of the college students consumed fruits and vegetables once per day and 1-3 times per week) respectively contrary to (WHO) recommended amount of five times per day.

The main factors influencing consumption of fruits and vegetables were freshness, health benefits, fruits and vegetables in season, taste/appearance, likeness/preference, prices in the market, availability of money to spend, lack of availability and variety of fruits produced on campus and lack of important places to buy the existing fresh fruits and vegetables. The College students agreed to the various suggested ways of improving the consumption of fruits and vegetables.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers recommend as follows.

1. The pattern of fruits and vegetables consumption by College students in the study area needs to be improved by health workers using mass media, health talks and one on one health education for the College students.
2. The College students need to be encouraged to have small gardens in their home environments to ensure availability of fruits and vegetables for their consumption all year round.
3. Government should provide infrastructural facilities to facilitate storage as well as preservation methods such as solar drying.
4. Policy and environmental approach can be used to improve availability of fruits and vegetables. Federal initiative such as the 'Let's move initiative', 'know your Farmer', 'know your food', 'support environmental and policy changes' to increase access to fruits and vegetables consumption.

5. To improve the consumption of fruits and vegetables among College students, storage facilities should be improved upon and nutritional education on the health benefits of consumption of fruits and vegetables should be organized for students. There should be provision of farmers' market on campus, availability of fruits and vegetables around resident halls and considerable amount of income should be budgeted on fruits and vegetables.

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